

Evidence base of Oncology Clinical Practice Guidelines – A bibliometric comparison of Germany and the UK

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This work builds on our study presented at last year's STI where we showed that the relevance of journals for clinical practice guidelines is independent from their impact factor (JIF). We expand on it in three ways: first by expanding our scope by comparing two countries, second by diving deeper into the characteristics of guideline references and third by exploring how these characteristics depend on national research context. We observe some overlap as well as considerable heterogeneity in the types of papers cited across the two different guideline programs. We also find that both German and UK guidelines preferentially cite national research, showing the importance of a local science base and the value of local journals. Compared to the UK, German guidelines have higher self-citation rates and cite significantly less research from Asia indicating possible bias.

1. Introduction

In this paper, we present our analysis of the literature cited in 48 British and German clinical practice guidelines (CPGs) on cancer, which are created to support the decision-making of physicians, patients, and other healthcare professionals. The Association of the Scientific Medical Societies (AWMF) is a scientific network consisting of 183 member societies that coordinates guideline activities and publishes medical recommendations for Germany. The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) is its UK counterpart and was founded in 1999 to provide evidence-based recommendations for healthcare (Wailoo et al., 2004). The processes and institutional arrangements guiding the creation of CPGs vary between countries and guideline bodies, but are generally aimed at systematically producing guidance reflecting the current state of knowledge relevant in specific clinical situations (Guthrie et al., 2019).

When gathering the best available evidence for diagnosis and treatment of illnesses, guideline developers scan the literature for evidence-based research and apply systematic criteria for the inclusion of studies. Like peer review, this can be interpreted as a quality marker for included studies. In addition, citations in CPGs can be interpreted as evidence that a study had a societal impact by guiding medical practice (Thelwall & Maflahi, 2016).

This paper is building on our previous study, where we proposed the Guideline Impact Factor (GLIF) and used it to show that the relevance of a journal in the development of clinical practice guidelines is independent from its impact factor (JIF). Guideline references can be used as an independent quality criterion for journals (Aman & Sorgatz, 2023). We also found evidence that common research evaluation practices solely relying on JIFs are undervaluing clinical, as well as local research outputs underpinning CPGs. This paper expands on these findings in three ways, first by expanding our scope with the inclusion of another country, second by diving deeper into the characteristics of guideline references and third by exploring how these characteristics depend on national research context.

Several studies have analyzed the evidence base of selected clinical practice guidelines in UK (e.g. Grant, 1999, 2000; Kryl et al., 2012; Lewison & Wilcox-Jay, 2003) showing that cited references are mostly clinical in their scope, up-to-date and highly cited. A study of references

in UK cancer guidelines showed that UK research papers are “overcited” (Lewison & Sullivan, 2008). Pentheroudakis et al. (2008) demonstrated that there is considerable heterogeneity in English language CPGs in aspects of guideline development, methodology, structure, implementation, and evaluation. However, the relationship between national research context and the evidence base used in CPGs remains understudied. In an effort to address this gap, we compare the body of evidence that underpins British and German oncology CPGs.

After giving an overview of our data, we compare the references by document types and fields of research. Then, we compare which countries contribute to the evidence base cited in CPGs and analyse the amount of author self-citations. Thereafter, we examine publication dates to see how long it takes for research to get incorporated into guidelines. Finally, we look at journals that publish research underpinning guidelines and compare their JIFs and GLIFs in order to gauge the relative importance of high prestige and mostly international journals versus lower prestige and local journals.

2. Data and Methods

Our study comprises 31 high-quality AWMF CPGs related to cancer, which were published between 2018 and 2022 and downloaded in January 2023 from the AWMF website. In order to compose a comparable set of UK CPGs, we identified and downloaded all 17 NICE CPGs related to cancer in October 2023 which were published between 2015 and 2023. German CPGs are usually condensed into one document which is updated regularly and supplemented by a small number of documents like diagnostic flowcharts. In contrast, NICE CPGs are usually spread across several dozen files, due to their continuous update process.

We had to build our own reference dataset, because databases such as Overton or BMJ Impact Analytics do not distinguish between excluded and included studies. AWMF CPGs list their references at the end of the document, so automatic text extraction was feasible, giving us a total of 26,287 references. Extracting included references from our set of NICE guidelines was much more difficult, because references can appear in different document sections and are spread across 186 PDFs. Our manual extraction yielded 12,626 references; unlike AWMF references these are not unique and often listed in multiple documents.

We separated reference strings into components such as authors, publication year, title, source, issue, pages, etc. and ran these against an in-house version of Web of Science (WoS) that includes publication data from 1980 until 2023. References that were not matched were revised by hand and searched in the online version of WoS to identify the right match in cases where guideline authors either made a mistake (for example missing authors, incomplete article titles or wrong journal abbreviations) or reference strings were malformed due to formatting errors. We were able to match 22,776 of 26,287 AWMF references in WoS (86.6 %) and 11,043 of 12,626 NICE references (87.5 %). Non-matched references include non-serial outputs, such as books, reports, websites, and journals not covered by WoS. Figure 1 shows that the share of matched references per AWMF CPG ranges between 75 % and 96 %.

Figure 1. Share of references matched in WoS and the share of references unmatched in 31 AWMF CPGs.

Similarly, Figure 2 shows that the share of matched references per NICE CPG ranges between 74 % and 96 %.

Figure 2. Share of references matched in WoS and the share of references unmatched in NICE CPGs.

The following analysis is based on the publications matched in WoS that were published between 1980 and 2023. The comparison includes 21,456 unique cited references in AWMF CPGs and 7,727 unique references cited in NICE CPGs. There are 985 unique references cited both in AWMF and in NICE CPGs. We assume that this “overlap” consists of high-quality publications because they passed peer-review and were judged relevant by two guideline bodies. Figure 3 illustrates the overlap between AWMF and NICE CPG references.

Figure 3. Overview of the number of unique references in the AWMF CPGs, NICE CPGs and the overlap between these two guideline bodies.

3. Results

3.1. Document types

In addition to WoS document types we were also able to identify PubMed document types for some of our publications (AMWF: 70.3 %; NICE: 68.8 %; overlap: 56.2 %).

As shown in Figure 4 AWMF references have a higher share of reviews than NICE references (13.2 % vs. 8.1 %), whereas NICE references cite proceedings and meeting abstracts more frequently than AWMF CPGs.

Figure 4. Document types in WoS and in PubMed for cited references in AWMF and NICE CPGs and the overlap.

Looking at the right-hand side of the figure it becomes evident that randomized controlled trials (RCT) - which are regarded as the gold standard for evaluating the effectiveness of clinical interventions - are the preferred evidence source in our overlap publication set which is also characterized by a higher share of systematic reviews. AWMF guidelines reference a much higher share of narrative reviews.

3.2. Field of research

Figure 5 shows to which of the approx. 250 WoS Subject Categories (SC) the cited references belong. The SCs are fractionally counted so that each bar adds up to 100 %. Aside from the broad SC Oncology and Medicine, General & Internal, AWMF CPGs emphasize Urology & Nephrology, followed by Surgery. NICE CPGs emphasize Surgery, Radiology, Nuclear Medicine and Endocrinology. What is striking is that the publications cited in the NICE CPGs have a comparatively high share of publications related to Endocrinology & Metabolism.

Figure 5. Subject Categories in WoS for cited references in AWMF and NICE CPGs and the overlap.

3.3. Country of origin

Affiliation data in WoS was used on a fractional basis to estimate the proportion of cited research that was conducted in a country. Figure 6 shows that guidelines are mostly drawing on research from the USA and the respective country for which the guideline is developed.

AWMF CPGs mostly cite research from USA, Germany, UK, Italy, and Canada, while NICE CPGs preferentially cite papers from USA, UK, China, Italy, and Germany. Interestingly, NICE guidelines cite more Chinese publications than AWMF CPGs. Despite the dominance of a few countries among cited papers, many other countries contributed to the publications. Papers cited in AWMF and NICE CPGs were linked to authors from 121 and 96 countries, respectively.

The analysis of the overlap publications shows that USA, UK, Italy and Germany are important contributors of research to the evidence base supporting both AWMF and NICE guidelines. The USA remain the largest contributor when we look at whole counts: More than 40 % of papers cited in AWMF CPGs have a US institution affiliation, and 30.5 % of the papers cited in NICE CPGs, respectively. In contrast, only 19.1 % of the cited references in AWMF CPGs have a German affiliation, whereas 17.8 % of cited references in NICE CPGs have authors affiliated in the UK.

Figure 6. Overview of the countries cited in the AWMF and NICE CPGs and in the overlap.

Comparing both countries also gives us interesting insight into the regionality of guideline references. 8.9 % of papers cited in AWMF CPGs are national publications with German affiliations only; NICE CPGs have a higher share with 9.9 % UK publications. Interestingly, 7.4 % of cited references in NICE CPGs refer to purely Chinese publications, whereas the share in AWMF references is only about 2.5 %, indicating potential bias.

3.4. Self-citations of guideline authors

Like all scientific citation practices, self-citations have a variety of functions and are used to different ends (Luukkonen, 1997). Arguably one of the most useful functions is that they link text to prior work without the need to repeat oneself.

But there is also concern about “illicit” self-citations among scholars, especially in fields like medicine (e.g. Shomoossi & Rad, 2023). We calculated self-citation rates in our set of CPGs by identifying all CPG authors of AWMF and NICE guidelines and matching the author names with the authors listed in the references. In total, 2008 authors have contributed to the AWMF CPGs compared to 301 authors who have participated in developing NICE guidelines. We find that 10.4 % of AWMF cited references are self-citations, whereas only 2.7 % of the references cited in NICE CPGs are self-citations. Self-citation rates in both sets are much lower than rates reported for journal articles, which range from 17 % for clinical medicine (Aksnes, 2003, p. 241) to 29.8 % for medicine (Pandita & Singh, 2017, p. 118). Moreover, Figure 7 illustrates the share of authors with self-citations in CPGs, differentiated according to the number of self-citations in the respective set of cited references. Whereas 60.9 % of AWMF CPG authors have no self-citation, this share is much higher among the NICE CPG authors (76.7 %).

Figure 7. Share of authors with self-citations in AWMF and NICE CPG references.

3.5. Knowledge cycle time

The “knowledge cycle time” (Grant, 1999) represents the average interval between the publication date of the CPGs and the publication date of the papers cited in the guidelines. Figure 8 illustrates the publication date of references cited in AWMF and NICE CPGs and in the overlap. The median publication date of AWMF and NICE CPGs is 2010, whereas the publication date of overlap references is 2009. The average publication date of AWMF CPGs is 2008.8, of NICE CPGs 2009.2 and of overlap references 2009.0, respectively. All references in our overlap set were published before 2019.

Figure 8. Knowledge cycle time of references in AWMF and NICE CPGs and the overlap.

3.6. JIF and Guideline Impact Factor (GLIF)

In line with our prior study (Aman & Sorgatz, 2023) – showing that the inclusion of studies in German CPGs does not depend on the JIF - we take the 2019 JIF, as it heavily increased for some medical journals from 2020 onwards due to Covid-19 related publications.

Figure 9 illustrates the cumulative distribution of JIF of references cited in AWMF and NICE CPGs and in overlap publications. With an average of 12.3 the JIF of cited references in AWMF CPGs is slightly higher than in the NICE CPGs (9.8) and even higher in the overlap (21.8). The median JIF of the cited references in AWMF CPGs is roughly 5.5, and about 4.2 in NICE CPGs. However, the median JIF of the overlap publications is 10.2 and thus much higher than for AWMF or NICE CPGs, indicating that they appeared in high impact journals.

Figure 9. Cumulative distribution of JIF of references cited in AWMF and NICE CPGs and in the overlap.

Figures 10 and 11 show that journal prestige measured by the JIF does not correlate with the importance of a journal as a source of guideline evidence both for German and British guidelines measured by the GLIF (both figures report Kendall's τ).

Figure 10. GLIF and JIF (2019) of journals cited in AWMF CPGs on cancer.

Figure 11. GLIF and JIF (2019) of journals cited in NICE CPGs on cancer.

4. Discussion

Clinical practice guidelines are intended to provide diagnostic, preventative and treatment information to bridge the gap between research and clinical practice (Kryl et al., 2012). The aim of this paper was to compare the evidence bases of oncology CPGs in Germany and UK. We observed considerable heterogeneity in the types of papers cited across the two different guideline programs.

Regarding document types, AWMF CPGs draw more on review articles while NICE CPGs include more meeting abstracts and proceedings. The overlap of cited references is characterized by a high share of randomized controlled trials and systematic reviews which is in line with their status as gold standard evidence. We observed some differences in fields of research cited but think that these variations are mainly driven by difference in scope of the CPGs and not by differences between guideline programs. Our findings are in line with prior research showing that guidelines are heavily relying on clinical research (Andersen, 2013; Grant, 2000; Lewison & Sullivan, 2008).

Our analysis of affiliations shows that there might be a selective reporting bias overciting research from USA, Western Europe, and the country of the guideline issuing body, while ignoring research from Asia. This bias of selective reporting is in accordance with previous studies, which found that cancer guidelines “overcite” US and UK research (e.g. Pallari et al. 2018). The local character of public health research is reflected in the relatively high level of national papers cited across guidelines, which also shows the importance of a local science base and the value of research contributions from local journals. The share of self-citations is much lower than the ones usually found in articles published in medical journals. We also find that this rate is much higher in AWMF CPGs than in NICE CPGs. Without further analysis we cannot provide any definite explanation for this difference.

Our findings of the knowledge cycle time corroborate earlier findings for UK CPGs that a significant share of publications cited were published within the 10 years prior to the release of the CPGs (Grant et al., 1999; Lewison & Sullivan, 2008). The overlap publications are not as up-date as publications exclusive to AWMF or NICE CPGs.

In line with our prior study (Aman & Sorgatz, 2023), we discovered that references in British as well as German CPGs on cancer are chosen independent of JIF-based journal prestige. This suggests that authors of clinical practice guidelines scan through different journals to find

relevant studies independent of impact factors. This is in line with a citation impact analysis of cited references in AWMF CPGs carried out by our colleagues (Traylor & Herrmann-Lingen, 2023).

There are several limitations to this study. The analysis is based only on cited references matched in WoS and considers only the successfully included papers, disregarding the papers that are potentially relevant to the topic but not cited in the guidelines or papers that are deliberately excluded. Without looking at the content, we also cannot say which approach is superior. The smaller number of references in NICE CPGs might signal a focus on the very best evidence but could also be missing important evidence. On the other hand, AWMF CPGs could be too inclusive and might provide references to studies that are not representing the best evidence.

Further research is needed to disentangle the various effects influencing the evidence base of CPGs including language, local research cultures, different guideline processes and institutional configurations as well as differences in the socioeconomic composition of working groups drafting guidelines.

5. Conclusion

The aim of evidence-based clinical practice guidelines is to translate the best available scientific knowledge on the benefits and harms of diagnostic and therapeutic interventions into clear, practicable recommendations for action. Research papers referenced in CPGs are an indication of their potential to impact health policy and practice. It is therefore important to understand the evidence base cited in CPGs. We observe some overlap as well as considerable heterogeneity in the types of papers cited across the two guideline programs.

The fact that AWMF and NICE CPGs do preferentially cite German and UK authors respectively, demonstrates the importance of a local science base and the value of publishing in local journals. However, the championing of local research should not lead one to ignore research from other regions like Asia, which seems to be the case with German guidelines. Developers of clinical practice guidelines should be aware of these biases favoring research from the US and European countries and be conscious of possible adverse effects on knowledge bases underpinning CPGs. Healthcare professionals should also be aware of this heterogeneity to enable effective decision making for tailored treatments, regardless of geographical location in Europe (Pallari et al., 2018).

Further research would benefit from coherent digital CPG references in an open database. This would ease comparable analyses and provide a rich source of information for funders, medical scientists, patients and other interested parties.

Open science practices

This research relies on the proprietary WoS database. Except for the raw reference strings of the studied clinical practice guidelines (which can be made available upon request) no new software or dataset was produced for this study.

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Competing interests

There are no competing interests.

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